

Participatory Variety Selection for Farmer's Identified Traits (From June to Sept.-October/ Monsoon Season, 2020) Online meeting on Sun Oct 4, 2020 10am - 11am

Participatory Variety Selection (PVS)

Fig. - Five State's partners participated in Online PVS meeting on 4 Oct 2020

Participatory Variety Selection (PVS) involves growing a number of crop varieties (either on-station or on-farm) and having farmers evaluate the crop varieties (for a review, see Witcombe, 2005). A range of PVS formats exist. In certain formats of PVS, farmers come together to a common plot to observe and rate the varieties on various aspects, including vegetative characteristics and characteristics of the final product, including yield and consumption-related traits. The sessions allow for interaction between farmers and researcher

Participatory varietal selection (PVS) helps:

- To shorten the period between varietal development and varietal adoption by farmers (3 years for PVS compared with 7 years for the conventional method);
- To strengthen farmers' autonomy and to increase their freedom to select varieties;

PVS: “Farmer Choice - Which Variety and Why?” / Farmer preferred Characteristics? / Why Farmers prefer and trust local/improved varieties of seeds?

- **Agronomic superiority:** Time of maturity, Diseases

- **Cooking qualities:** Taste, Boiling time, Self life after cooking, Consumption
- **Marketability**
- **Nutrition quality**
- **Women selected seeds based on desired traits** such as **drought resistance, ease of preparation, nutritional value, and pest and disease resistance**

PVS cycle

The participatory varietal selection cycle takes 3 years, including seed production in the dry season (Fig. 5). In year 1, an observational nursery is established on a farmer's plot or a plot in the research station. In year 2, the varieties selected are tested at two levels: multi-location trials or '*mother trials*' conducted by scientists with or without farmer collaboration; and scattered tests or '*baby trials*' in farmers' fields, which are the responsibility of the farmer and are carried out using farmers' management practices. At this stage, the varietal release committee of the ministry of agriculture joins the evaluating farmers and scientists to ascertain the Value for Cultivation and Utilisation (VCU) and the Distinction Uniformity and Stability (DUS), which are the two indices of evaluation prior to varietal release (registration into the official catalog). In year 3, baby trials are repeated by farmers (to account for annual variability in weather) for confirmation and possible extension to other farmers. VCU and DUS are also checked at this stage. At the baby trial, the observations of both experimenting and visiting farmers are taken into account.

Participative varietal selection cycle

PVS

Organized evaluation visits

During the season, three guided visits are undertaken by all stakeholders at the tillering, heading/flowering and maturity stages of the rice plants to comment on the agronomic characters and productivity of the varieties (Annex 2).

- 1st visit during the vegetative phase: Comments are recorded on tillering capacity, emergence vigor, crop establishment, tolerance of biotic and abiotic stresses. The practical exchanges between participants will relate to cropping practices (secondary application of urea, crop maintenance, roguing, etc.)
- 2nd visit at reproductive phase: Comments are recorded on the crop establishment, timing, homogeneity, etc. The practical exchanges will be on cropping practices and post-harvest activities.
- 3rd visit at maturity phase: Comments will be on timing, homogeneity, panicle characteristics (exsertion, branching, density, length, number of grains, etc.) and quality. The practical exchanges will cover cropping practices (secondary application of urea, crop maintenance, roguing, etc.) and post-harvest activities.

Each above evaluation visit (Total Three visits) has the Following 7 steps for one day training:

Step 1: At the beginning of each session, the scientist in charge introduces the trial and outlines its objectives while highlighting the purpose of the exercise. Participants have one hour to visit the plot.

Step 2: At the end of this first phase, farmers are placed in groups of 10 men or 10 women. Every group member evaluates the varieties separately. A fact sheet is allocated to every farmer (Annex 2).

Step 3: Every farmer should respond to the following: ‘Among all the varieties, select 3 to 5 that you would like to sow in your farm and explain why.’ Standing in front of his or her selected varieties, the farmer gives his or her reasons.

Step 4: After selecting his or her best varieties, each farmer must answer another question: ‘Which rice varieties do you think are not performing well and why?’

Step 5: This step requires each farmer to respond to another series of questions: ‘What are the most significant characteristics for you when selecting rice varieties to grow in your farm? After listing these characteristics, rate each one (1 = very significant; 2 = significant; 3 = more or less significant; 4 = less significant; 5 = not at all significant).’

Step 6: collection of forms

Step 7: Wrap up the meeting and review the evaluation + video recording for farmers responses

YEAR 1 – SHEET 2: FARMER EVALUATION

For farmers involved in the evaluation of the varieties cultivated in the garden (1 sheet per farmer)

A. General Information

1. Name of the farmer: _____
2. Age: _____
3. Sex: _____
4. Village (origin): _____

B. Farmer evaluation at tillering and heading/maturity

1. Garden Visit Date: _____
2. Which rice varieties do you want to sow on your farm and why?

Variety (number)	Reasons for selection	More detailed explanations	Score

3. Which rice varieties do you think are not performing, or which varieties would you not like to sow on your farm and why?

Variety (number)	Reasons why you do not like these varieties	More detailed explanations

5. Can you evaluate the extent to which these traits are shown by the variety you have just selected? Check "x" in the column (a, b or c) that tallies with the selection of the variety (write the name and number of the variety).

Trait	Variety																	
	a	b	c	a	b	c	a	b	c	a	B	c	a	b	c	a	b	c
1.																		
2.																		
3.																		
4.																		
5.																		
6.																		
7.																		
8.																		
9.																		
10.																		

a= very good; b= good; c= bad
